

METHODOLOGICAL PECULIARITIES OF DEVELOPING ENGLISH VOCABULARY COMPETENCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL (ON THE EXAMPLE OF GAME TECHNOLOGY)

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Abstract. *In the article it is discussed about the advantages, benefits and specific methods of teaching and various methods of Game Technology in the process of teaching and learning English lexicon. The article consists of annotation, keywords, introduction, main part, conclusion and list of used literature.*

Keywords: *methods, techniques, game, vocabulary, lexic features, lexical competence.*

INTRODUCTION

After the independence of our country, interest in teaching foreign languages increased and many opportunities were created for young people. As an example, the views of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev put forward at an expanded meeting on the development of foreign languages and professional teaching system in schools on January 20, 2022, the meeting discussed the issues of improving the quality of teaching foreign languages and directing students to the profession. According to him, "A child who has learned a profession and language from school is a great achievement of our society, a problem that he does not know," says Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Proof of these points is that to introduce this experience, one city and two districts are selected from each region, studying the conditions of more than 2 thousand schools in them, the qualifications of educators, the interest of students in vocational and foreign languages. In order to qualitatively teach foreign languages, schools are being instructed to attract "Language-owning" educators, to implement language-teaching experience, textbooks, and programs of presidential schools. Such a high level of attention, which is personally paid to the qualitative teaching and excellent learning of Foreign Languages by a citizen, imposes on the young generation and officials such a responsible task as being able to move even more on the path of teaching and learning foreign languages and make the most of the conditions created.

The goal of learning any foreign language is to be able to communicate fluently in that language. Teaching and learning foreign languages is a long and perfect process. He requires regular labor from a person and work on himself. It is clear that the use of various interactive games in the process of teaching foreign languages to grow oral speech skills makes learning a foreign language not boring, but rather interesting and a hobby. Interactive games the fact that language learners behave much more fluently encourages even shy learners to participate in these games is effective in applying interactive games especially to order grammar and vocabulary.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The game as a specific process of educational activity has a special place in the methodology. Game forms of learning are indispensable in learning a foreign language. They help at different stages of the study of certain linguistic phenomena to understand the logic and system features of a foreign language environment. For children, the game – the main activity, so the

lessons of foreign language teachers preferring game forms of work on the material is increasing [1].

The game in the English lesson has a multi-stage goal – teaching, developing and educational: helps to explain certain language features; develops the skills of learning activities; forms interest in the subject under study; game technologies can be used at any stage of the lesson; presentation of new material; automation of the use of new material in practice; consolidation of the acquired knowledge; as a reference point to verify the assimilation of information.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In addition, playing techniques guarantee a positive learning outcome for both the student and the teacher, because:

- all students are included in the learning process (emotional games captures children);
- each participant of the game can show their personal qualities (spontaneity of joint activity shows not only the learning abilities of the child, but also his character traits, helps to socialize in the circle of peers and teachers);
- even the difficult linguistic material can be documented is available for children;
- the teacher feels professional satisfaction, because with the help of the game, not only the assimilation of the material goes faster, but the lesson as a whole takes place on an emotional rise.

However, despite all the positive aspects of gaming activities, there are a number of points that make some Methodists cautiously relate to the introduction of gaming moments in the English lesson:

- game elements distract from the educational material (in the process of playing the child is much more important to focus on the conditions of the game, not on its content);
- there is a difficulty in maintaining discipline in the classroom (to explain the rules take a long time – children are distracted from the educational material);
- children are included in the game at the same time (someone is too late, and someone does not want to play at all, because they do not associate the entertainment form of activity with the lesson);
- students of any age are difficult to get out of the game, to focus on other forms of work;
- the teacher has to spend a lot of time preparing didactic material for the game;
- games in the classroom often provoke conflicts between children.

There are several classifications of games in the English lesson that differ:

- by the nature of the game (mobile, static, role-playing);
- form (puzzles, crosswords, imitation);
- goals (games for the assimilation of educational information, consolidation, games to change the type of activity, to get acquainted);
- nature of didactic materials (phonetic, lexical, communicative)

Communicative: Didactic material for games should be selected with great care. The most popular in the process of learning English communicative games. They help to realize the main goal of teaching a foreign language – to learn the semantic perception of foreign language speech and to form the skills of using language structures in untrained communication. For communication games methodologists in foreign language are advised to use audio application. For example, *"Who is the champion?"* Students are invited to listen to an excerpt of the dialogue and write down all the adjectives sounded in it. For younger children, you can offer to paint the scene picture with colors, as did the participants of the dialogue presented in the recording. Middle-

aged students like the simulation game *"Like a fish"*. The teacher offers to view the video clip without sound. Children should voice seen plot [2].

The game *"A Pop Star"* helps to train the skills of Dialogic speech. Each student is a popular pop star who needs to make an original rider out of 5 unusual things for touring. Students exchange lists and ask for an explanation of a position.

Role-playing nature of the game is most preferred in English lessons. Since, in addition to the implementation of educational goals, such games form children's ability to work in a team, develop a healthy spirit of competition. For example, when studying the theme *"Colors"* children are invited to play *"Who is faster?"* On the Board, the teacher writes the numbers at random, calls two (or more) students and begins to quickly call the numbers. Children have to circle the word with chalk. The winner is the one who has not made mistakes and has not lost. High school students like the game *"Investigator"*. The group is divided into three teams-investigation teams. The leader of each team asks to find the missing family member, gives a detailed description, and "investigators" should draw the most accurate sketch. The winner is the team that made a more accurate picture of the description.

Choosing a game for an English lesson for kids, you should pay special attention to the outdoor activities. For example, games-songs: children listen to a song and repeat the actions of which it is sung. For those who are just starting to get acquainted with the language will be interesting game *"Stand in a circle"*: on the asphalt or a large sheet of paper (you can also use a Mat for Twister) drawn circles with the letter inside (you can repeat the same letter several times). The teacher calls a letter, the task of the children to find her and stand in a circle.

Each time, starting work with a new class, the teacher faces the task as quickly as possible to remember the names of children. This is especially true for young teachers, whose experience does not allow you to quickly navigate in the children's team. It is equally important to know the names of the students themselves, especially if it is a new class. Universal game on familiarity is *"Snowball."* The teacher calls his name, and the students repeat in a circle the name of the teacher and all who introduced themselves before. Such a game can be complicated for the middle level (especially if the children there are already familiar), adding one sentence about Hobbies or some specific action ("I am Nataly. I am scratching my head now"). In high school is very interesting for children game *"Numbers in my life"* The teacher (and then the children) writes several numbers on the Board (date of birth, age of the beloved dog, etc.). The task of children is to guess what they mean in the life of this man.

Game moments in training activities—mandatory stages of the lesson

The task of the teacher to introduce them dosed, and even with the addition of new material to rely more on what children already know. Then the goal of gaming technology and learning a foreign language in General will be achieved easily and harmoniously.

Modern education is characterized by the complexity of curricula and the growth of information not only in secondary but also in primary school. As a result, younger students experience great psycho-emotional and physical overload. Psychologists have determined that younger students are characterized by increased emotionality, mobility, fatigue from uniformity, integrity of perception of the world. Primary education needs to be tailored to these characteristics and can be based on integrative learning.

Under integrative learning we understand the Association of educational activities with other significant for this age activities: visual, musical, labor, physical, theatrical, gaming, etc.

Thus, we are not talking about the unification of different academic disciplines, that is, interdisciplinary integration, and the interaction of different activities in the course of educational and cognitive activities. This greatly contributes to the involvement of all students in the cognitive process. A positive result is achieved, first of all, by the fact that in the created psychological environment of emotional tension, negative factors are neutralized or completely removed[3].

In the organization of teaching English language to conduct classes following the integrative species:

English lesson plus musical activities (singing, music, rhythm, etc.)

English lesson plus visual activities (drawing, application, modeling)

English lesson plus physical activities

English lesson plus theatrical activities.

English lesson plus game activities

School traditions are inextricably linked with the child's play activities at all stages of his education at school. The game takes an important place in the life of the younger student, being for him a means of learning reality. Based on the characteristics of the psychological development of the younger student, one of which is the predominance of the emotional sphere over the intellectual, it is impossible not to assess the potential of the game as an emotional factor.

Games in foreign language lessons should be an integral part of the methodical organization of the lesson. We all know that, having come home from school, younger students, first of all, go to their toys. The plots of the games are the most unpretentious, however, such a game gives children incomparable pleasure. This feature should be taken into account and widely used in the educational process, especially when teaching a foreign language, as it appeals mainly to the memory of students. The memory of younger students is involuntary, they quickly and easily remember what he likes.

CONCLUSION

In the lesson we are dealing with a special kind of games – language games. Language minimum, which is one of the components of the content of learning a foreign language, includes language units at different levels of the language, the totality of which form the lexical, grammatical and phonetic minima. Hence, there are the following language games: lexical, grammatical and phonetic. Language games allow you to make the learning process interesting. This is a powerful incentive to learn a foreign language. The atmosphere of enthusiasm, joy, feeling the power of tasks – all this has a beneficial effect on learning outcomes. It is easier to assimilate the language material, and with it there is a sense of satisfaction.

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